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Humero – bicipito - articularis: a rare accessory muscle of the arm

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ABSTRACT

Background: Anomalies related to the musculature of the upper limb are extremely important for plastic and orthopedic surgeons in their clinical practice. The present study reports the presence of a rare accessory muscle in the flexor compartment of the arm with its morphological description and also highlights its clinical relevance.

Materials and Methods: We encountered a rare accessory muscle in the region of upper arm of an adult male Indian cadaver in the Anatomy department. The anatomical details of this accessory muscle were studied in detail and appropriate photograph was taken.

Results: An accessory muscle in the flexor compartment of the right upper arm was observed. The muscle originated from the proximal part of the humeral shaft and displayed insertion into the lateral border of the short head of biceps brachii. Its fibers also blended

with the fibrous capsule of the shoulder joint.

Conclusions: The plethora of muscular variations in this important anatomic area is of utmost significance to the surgeon performing reconstructive and explorative procedures.

Key Words: Accessory muscle, biceps brachii, upper arm, variations, additional belly

INTRODUCTION

The proximal attachment of biceps brachii is classically described as a long head attached to the supraglenoid tubercle and a short head to the coracoid process. Distally, the bellies fuse to form a common tendon inserting into radial tuberosity and bicipital aponeurosis. Many researchers have described an additional head of biceps brachii in mammals. [1,2,3] This third head has been reported with varying frequency in other populations such as Japanese 18%, Chinese 8%, European whites 10% Brazilian whites 20%. [4]. It has been reported unilaterally [5] as well as bilaterally [6].

The present study reports an accessory muscle belly originating from upper part of shaft of humerus, joining the short head of biceps and fibrous capsule of the shoulder joint in an adult Indian human cadaver. A thorough knowledge of the complexities of variations in this region is of utmost significance for the hand surgeons undertaking reconstructive procedures. The clinical significance of this accessory muscle is vital for the orthopedic surgeons in view of its probable association with unusual bony displacements subsequent to fracture. [7] The objective of our report is to illustrate in detail the topography of this variant muscle belly and to discuss its functional and clinical relevance in detail.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present muscular variation was found in the right arm of a 40-year-old male cadaver during educational dissection session of preclinical students. The flexor compartment of the upper arm was dissected. The disposition and morphology of the anomalous muscle was examined. The topographical anatomy of the muscle in relation to surrounding structures was studied and appropriate photograph was taken.

RESULTS

A fleshy muscle belly was seen arising from the proximal part of the humeral shaft impinging on the lesser tubercle. (Figure 1). It had a linear bony attachment measuring about 4.1cms. The fibers were directed upwards and medially fusing with the lateral border of the short head of biceps brachii.

Fig 1: Dissection of Flexor Compartment of right upper arm

* Accessory muscle- (Humero-bicipito-Articularis)

- a. Short head of biceps brachii
- b. Long head of biceps brachii
- c. Anterior circumflex Humeral Vessels

- d. Fibrous capsule of shoulder Joint.

Few slips from the upper part of the muscle were also seen to blend with antero-medial portion of fibrous capsule of the shoulder joint. This accessory muscle crossed superficial to the anterior circumflex humeral vessels. Its innervation was derived from the musculocutaneous nerve. No unusual morphology was observed in the left upper limb.

DISCUSSION

The present investigation reports a rare unilateral accessory muscle in the region of the upper arm. This additional muscle belly did not display attachment to coracobrachialis or the brachialis muscle. However, it was found to fuse with the short head of biceps whereas in a large number of earlier cases the

accessory muscle joined the tendon of biceps brachii. [8, 9]

Considering the evolutionary aspect, the third head of biceps could represent a remnant of long head of coracobrachialis, which is an ancestral hominid muscle [3]. In humans, the two short heads have fused; trapping the musculocutaneous nerve in between and the third head has been suppressed [10]

Three heads of coracobrachialis have been described [11], the proximal one being attached to the humerus close to the lesser tubercle. This proximal head may extend into the capsule of the shoulder joint or the surgical neck of the humerus. The supernumerary head represents the tuberculo-septal head of the gibbon, from the phylogenetic point of view. [12]

Varying attachments of the third head of the biceps such as origin from the deltoid or brachialis and insertion into pronator teres or radial tuberosity have also been described in literature. [5, 6] Based on the relationship and attachments, the accessory belly encountered in the present study seems to be derived from the anterior compartment of the arm. [13] Many variants of coracobrachialis such as a coracoscapularis, coracobrachialis brevis have been reported. [11, 14]

An accessory coracobrachialis muscle has been described whose tendon was found to be attached to the articular capsule and lesser tubercle while distally it extended till the distal arm. [15]. In our study, the belly was fleshy throughout and was confined to the proximal humeral shaft. The explanation for this accessory belly could be postulated on the basis of ontogeny. Individual muscles originate from a mixture of segmental myotomes [16].

Presumably the muscle observed in the present study also had a developmental origin from a number of myotomes extending from the region of surgical neck to proximal humeral shaft, which by virtue of its topography may be linked to the biceps or coracobrachialis. Persistence of some cells between biceps and coracobrachialis or brachialis may account for this anomalous muscle. Few scientists reported a bilateral and symmetrical accessory head of biceps brachii in 60% of the cases studied, whereas 33.3% exhibited the same unilaterally on the left side more commonly than the right. They also found in their study, that the least common variant displayed a dual fascial origin from the lateral aspect of short head of biceps [17]. The anatomical disposition of this accessory muscle in our study differs from previous reports since it was interposed between the long and short heads of biceps brachii.

Different sites of origin for the third head of biceps have been described. It could be attached to the antero-medial surface of humerus, tendon of deltoid muscle and deltoid fascia. [5,7,15] A rare case of a four-headed biceps brachii muscle has been cited, in which the second head originated from the humerus and later joined the tendon of biceps brachii. [8]

An association between musculocutaneous and median nerves and supernumerary heads of biceps brachii was demonstrated in 13.2% of the dissected upper limbs. [18] They observed that most of these heads arose from the anteromedial surface of humerus and/or from medial intermuscular septum. It was found that the additional head fused with short head of biceps least commonly. In the present study, however the accessory muscle

was found to fuse with the short head of biceps.

An unusual origin of accessory head of biceps was reported, which appeared closest to our finding of accessory muscle belly, as it also interposed between the long and short heads. [19] However, in their case it originated from the distal part of pectoralis major, quite close to the cephalic vein.

Although earlier studies have described varied origins of supernumerary heads of biceps brachii, it is unlikely that the anomalous muscle encountered in this dissected specimen represents a variant of third head. The reason for the above is the orientation of the fibers and origin from humeral shaft and insertion into short head of biceps along with blending with the shoulder joint capsule.

The anatomical description of the anomalous muscle encountered in the present study reasonably justifies for designating it as humero-bicipito-articularis. In the present study, it originated from the humeral shaft and overlapped the anterior circumflex humeral vessels before joining the short head of biceps. The crucial presence of this accessory muscle over these vessels could possibly lead to compression and may thus jeopardize the circulation. Interestingly, a few slips of the accessory muscle were seen blending with the fibrous capsule of shoulder joint. This observation could be viewed as an attempt to strengthen the shoulder joint by rendering the rotator cuff richer in terms of muscles contributing to it.

The presence of an additional muscle may have functional and clinical implications. [13] Researchers have reported an enhancement of flexion by an additional head of biceps. [7] Notably, the fibers of the accessory

muscle were inclined supero-medially before joining the short head of biceps brachii. This could possibly alter the biomechanics of the biceps brachii. This rare variant belly could prove to be useful for reconstructive surgery such as after mastectomy or in cases of facial nerve palsy [15, 20]. Additionally, it may be used in contour deformities of the infraclavicular and anterior axillary area or as a transposition flap. [21]

MRI and CT scans play a significant role in evaluation of anatomical and pathological lesions of the upper extremity as well as serve as a guide for planning surgical resections. Thus the presence of this rare accessory muscle could constitute a puzzle while interpreting CT and MRI scans of upper extremity. Therefore a thorough anatomical insight into the anomalies of this region is extremely important.

CONCLUSIONS

Awareness of possible muscular variations in the upper limb is relevant for clinicians, especially to surgeons undertaking reconstructive procedures and to radiologists while interpreting CT and MRI scans.

REFERENCES

1. Dobson GE. Notes on anatomy of cercopithecus callithricus. Proceedings of Zoological society 1881; London: 812-18.
2. LeDouble AF. Traite des variations du systeme musculaire de l'homme. 2 Librarie C.Reinwald 1897; Paris.

3. Sonntag CF. On Anatomy, physiology and pathology of orang-utan. Proc Zool Soc 1924; 24:349-80.
4. Bergman RA, Thompson SA, Afifi AK. Catalogue of human variations. 1984. Munich: Urban & Schwarzenberg: 27-30.
5. Ozan H, Atasever A, Sinav A, Simsek C, Basar R. An unusual insertion of accessory biceps brachii muscle. Acta Anat Nippon 1997; 72:515-19.
6. Nakatani T, Tanaka S, Mizukami S. Bilateral four headed biceps brachii : Median nerve and Brachial artery passing through a tunnel formed by muscle slip from accessory head. Clin Anat 1998; 11:209-12.
7. Swieter MG & Carmichael SW. Bilateral three headed biceps brachii muscle. Anat Anaz 1980; 148:346-49.
8. Vazquez T, Rodri Quez, Niedenfuhr M, Parkin I, Sanudo JR. A rare case of four headed biceps brachii muscle with double piercing by musculocutaneous nerve. Surg Radiol Anat 2003; 25(5-6): 462-4.
9. Abu Hijleh-MF. Three headed biceps brachii muscle associated with duplicated musculocutaneous nerve. Clin Anat 2005; 18(5):376-9.
10. McMinn RMH. Last's Anatomy, regional and applied, 8th Ed. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone.; 1990, 79-80.
11. Wood J. On human muscular variations and their relation to comparative anatomy. J Anat Physiol 1867; 1:44-59.
12. Kudo K, Fukuyama U, Yoshino T, Bando K, Li M. Anatomical statistics of north Chinese male biceps brachii muscle. Hiroasaki Med J 1951; 4:18-26.
13. El Naggar MM, Zahir FI. Two bellies of coracobrachialis muscle associated with third head of biceps brachii. Clin Anat 2001; 14:379-82.
14. Macalister A. Additional observations on muscular anomalies in human anatomy (third series), with a catalogue of principal muscular variations hitherto published. Trans R Irish Acad 1875; 25:1-134.
15. Kopuz C, Icten N & Yildirim M. A rare accessory coracobrachialis muscle: A rev of lit. Surg Radiol Anat 1992; 24:406-10.
16. Chiak R. Ontogenesis of skeleton and intrinsic muscles of human hand and foot. Adv Anat Embryol Cell Biol 1972; 46:1-194.
17. Asvat R, Candler P, Sarmiento EE. High incidence of third head of biceps brachii in South African population. J Anat 1993; 182:101-4.

18. Kosugi K, Shibata S & Yamashita H. Supernumerary head of biceps brachii and branching pattern of musculocutaneous nerve in Japanese. *Surg Radiol Anat* 1992; 14:175-85.
19. Sargon MF, Tincali D & Hamidi Celik H. An unusual origin of accessory head of biceps brachii. *Clin Anat* 1996; 9:160-2.
20. Taylor GI, Cichowitz A, Ang SG, Seneviratne S, Ashton M. Comparative anatomical study of gracilis and coracobrachialis-implication for facial reanimation. *Plast Reconstr Surg* 2003;112:20-30.
21. Hobar PC, Rohrich RJ & Mickel TJ. The Coracobrachialis flap for coverage of exposed axillary vessels: a salvage procedure. *Plast Reconstr Surg* 1990; 85:801-4.